

Chaco Culture

also known as “Ancestral Pueblo (Pueblo II)”, “Ancestral Four Corners (Pueblo II)”, “Anasazi (Pueblo II)”

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Entry tags: Keresan, Native American (North American) Religions, Religious Group, Language, Unknown

The Chaco Culture refers to the Indigenous society of the Four Corners region of the U.S. Southwest from approximately AD 800-1200 that participated in a religious tradition focused on the monumental center at Chaco Canyon in northwestern New Mexico. Chaco-style Great House architecture, roads, and ceramic designs are found throughout a 100,000 sq. km region of the U.S. Southwest comprising what is known as the Chaco World or Chaco Regional System. Experts debate the significance of this widespread cultural pattern (e.g., whether the Chaco World was an integrated polity), but most agree that a compelling religious tradition was central to Chaco Canyon’s regional prominence and the spread of Chacoan architecture. The inhabitants of the Chaco World are ancestral to contemporary Pueblo and Diné (Navajo) cultures in the U.S. Southwest. Evidence for Chacoan religion is derived from the analysis of archaeological materials and also inferred through ethnographic analogy with descendant Pueblo and Diné (Navajo) cultures. Many Chacoan Great Houses and roads form alignments towards prominent landforms and astronomical events (specifically, solstices, equinoxes, and the lunar standstill cycle), suggesting a religious focus on sacred geography and astronomy. Chacoan religion also emphasized rainfall and moisture as suggested by extensive offering deposits of shell and turquoise, the destinations of many ceremonial roads at watery places, as well as the ongoing prominence of rainmaking ceremonialism among descendant cultures today. Key religious practices likely included pilgrimages to Chaco Canyon (though this interpretation is debated); commemoration of astronomical events; rituals utilizing Mesoamerican exotic goods including cacao, macaws, and copper bells; dances and gatherings in Great Kivas (circular, semi-subterranean ritual structures) and plazas; ritualized processions and races on roads; and making offerings of turquoise, shell, jet, and other stones. There is substantial evidence for an elite class in Chacoan society who lived in Great Houses, and many scholars posit that their elevated status derived from religious knowledge. Descendant Pueblo and Diné people state that many of their ongoing ceremonial practices originated at Chaco Canyon. Their oral traditions describe the Chaco Era to have been a time when certain members of society leveraged religious powers (e.g., control over the weather) and thereby gained social status and authority. While practices that developed during the Chaco Era remain core components of Pueblo and Diné religious life, the social structures in which they were/are practiced transformed radically in the centuries following the decline of Chaco Canyon as a regional center.

Date Range: 800 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Chaco World

Region tags: North America, United States of America, U.S. Southwest

The extent of known Chaco-style Great Houses.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Van Dyke, Ruth M. 2007. *The Chaco Experience: Landscape and Ideology at the Center Place*. Santa Fe (NM): School for Advanced Research Press.

– Source 2: Lekson, Stephen H. 2015. *The Chaco Meridian: One Thousand Years of Political and Religious Power in the Ancient Southwest* 2nd ed. ed. Lanham (MD): Rowman & Littlefield.

– Source 3: Mills, Barbara J. 2002. "Recent Research on Chaco: Changing Views on Economy, Ritual, and Society." *Journal of Archaeological Research* 10 (1): 65-117. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41053181>.

Reference: Van Dyke, Ruth M.. *The Chaco Experience: Landscape and Ideology at the Center Place*. Santa Fe: School for Advanced Research Press, 2007.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *The Chaco Meridian: One Thousand Years of Political and Religious Power in the Ancient Southwest*. 2nd ed... Lanham : Rowman & Littlefield, 2015.

Reference: Mills, Barbara J.. "Recent Research on Chaco: Changing Views on Economy, Ritual, and Society". *Journal of Archaeological Research* 10 (2002): 65-117. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1014564624013>.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.chacoarchive.org/>

Notes: The Chaco Archive is an online database providing access to a variety of information (excavation data, photographs, etc.) related to the archaeology of Chaco Canyon and its larger world.

– Source 1 URL: solsticeproject.org

Notes: The Solstice Project website contains academic research papers, links to videos, and other information about the role of astronomy in Chaco's religion.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Trade goods provide the clearest evidence for cultural contact between the Chaco Culture and other religious groups. The Chacoans obtained shell artifacts from the Pacific Coast and Gulf of California, but they were probably acquired through trade with the Hohokam culture in the Phoenix / Tucson Basin (Nelson 2006:350). Macaws, cacao, and copper bells were imported to Chaco Canyon from Mesoamerica. Macaws may have come from Tamaulipas (Gilman et al. 2014) or an as-of-yet unidentified breeding center in northern Mexico / southern Arizona (George et al. 2018). Cacao likely was obtained through trade with the Aztatlán culture of Nayarit and Sinaloa (Mathiowetz 2019). Copper bells came from west Mexico (Nelson 2006:349-50). The Chacoans also acquired turquoise from a variety of sources across the western and southwestern United States (Hull et al. 2014). Others have suggested that contemporaneous groups living in the Rio Grande Valley and Mimbres Valley defined their cultural identity and religious practices in contrast to Chacoan ways (Fowles 2013; Lekson 2015:46-48).

Reference: Fowles, Severin M.. *An Archaeology of Doings: Secularism and the Study of Pueblo Religion*. Santa Fe: School for Advanced Research Press, 2013.

Reference: George, Richard J., and et al.. "Archaeogenomic Evidence from the Southwestern US Points to a Pre-hispanic Scarlet Macaw Breeding Colony". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 115, no. 35 (2018): 8740–45. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1805856115> .

Reference: Gilman, Patricia A., Marc Thompson, and Kristina C. Wyckoff. "Ritual Change and the Distant: Mesoamerican Iconography, Scarlet Macaws, and Great Kivas in the Mimbres Region of Southwestern New Mexico.". *American Antiquity* 79, no. 1 (2014): 90–107. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.7183/0002-7316.79.1.90> .

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *The Chaco Meridian: One Thousand Years of Political and Religious Power in the Ancient Southwest*. 2nd ed... Lanham : Rowman & Littlefield, 2015.

Reference: Mathiowetz, Michael D.. "A History of Cacao in West Mexico: Implications for Mesoamerica and U.S. Southwest Connections". *Journal of Archaeological Research* 27 (2019): 287–333. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-018-9125-7>.

Reference: Nelson, Ben A.. "Mesoamerican Objects and Symbols in Chaco Canyon Contexts". In *The Archaeology of Chaco Canyon: An Eleventh-century Pueblo Regional Center*, edited by Stephen H. Lekson, 339–71. Santa Fe: School of American Research Press, 2006.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There is a general drop in violent conflict throughout the Chaco World during the 11th century in what is known as the "Pax Chaco" (LeBlanc 1999; Lekson 2002). Violence remained a reality of the Chaco World, however. Harrod (2013) provides bioarchaeological evidence for the use of violence by Chacoan elites as a strategy of social control, and Lekson (2002) interprets the evidence of 11th and 12th century "extreme processing events" as acts perpetuated by Chacoan forces punishing those inimical to the Chacoan social order. Certainly, violence increases, especially in the northern San Juan region (where the nucleus of population shift in the 12th century, following the decline of Chaco Canyon as a regional center. "The collapse of the Chacoan system in the mid-1100s brought violence to unprecedented levels in our area [the northern San Juan / Central Mesa Verde regions], perhaps in the form of score settling as old (but apparently resented) power structures fell apart" (Kohler et al. 2009:289).

Reference: LeBlanc, Steven A. . *Prehistoric Warfare in the American Southwest*. Salt Lake City.: University of Utah Press, 1999.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H. . "War in the Southwest, War in the World". *American Antiquity* 67, no. 4 (2002): 607–24. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/1593794> .

Reference: Harrod, Ryan P. . Chronologies of Pain and Power: Violence, Inequality, and Social Control Among Ancestral Pueblo Populations (AD 850-1300). Phd Dissertation. Las Vegas: Department of Anthropology, University of Nevada, Las Vegas, 2013.

Reference: Kohler, Timothy A., Sarah Cole, and Stanca Ciupe. "Population and Warfare: A Test of the Turchin Model in Pueblo Societies". In *Pattern and Process in Cultural Evolution*, edited by Stephen Shennan, 277-95. Berkeley: University of California Press, 2009.

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: At present, there is no evidence of Chacoan violent conflict with outside groups.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The nature of Chaco's political organization is highly contentious (see, for example, Lekson 2018; Mills 2018), though most scholars would agree that Chacoan religion was deeply entwined with the political authority of elites in Chaco Canyon.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *A Study of Southwestern Archaeology*. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, 2018.

Reference: Mills, Barbara J. . "What's New in Chaco Research?". *Antiquity* 92, no. 364 (2018): 855-69.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 80000

Notes: "current estimates range from 10,000-200,000 (with most between 20,000-50,000) persons in the entire Chaco World at its peak in the tenth and eleventh centuries AD(Mills 2018:864). Lekson (2015:11) proposes the population of the Chaco World was between 62,000-100,000 people.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *The Chaco Meridian: One Thousand Years of Political and Religious Power in the Ancient Southwest*. 2nd ed... Lanham : Rowman & Littlefield, 2015.

Reference: Mills, Barbara J. . "What's New in Chaco Research?". *Antiquity* 92, no. 364 (2018): 855–69.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Field doesn't know

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: High-status burials in Chaco Canyon are widely interpreted as leaders with some degree of religious authority (Lekson 2015; Mills 2018:860; Plog and Heitman 2010).

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *The Chaco Meridian: One Thousand Years of Political and Religious Power in the Ancient Southwest*. 2nd ed... Lanham : Rowman & Littlefield, 2015.

Reference: Mills, Barbara J. . "What's New in Chaco Research?". *Antiquity* 92, no. 364 (2018): 855–69.

Reference: Plog, Stephen, and Carrie Heitman. "Hierarchy and Social Inequality in the American Southwest, A.D. 800–1200". *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 107, no. 46 (2010): 19619–26.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: The presence of two tiers of Great House architecture -- those in Chacoan Canyon (first order) and outliers (second order) -- are suggestive of hierarchy among Chacoan religious leaders

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Field doesn't know

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There may be two tiers of religious hierarchical leadership in the Chaco World, with the inhabitants of Great Houses within Chaco Canyon overseeing leaders living in the inhabitants of outlier Great Houses throughout the Chaco World. Such an idea has been proposed (Lekson 2015; Stuart 2014).

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *The Chaco Meridian: One Thousand Years of Political and Religious Power in the Ancient Southwest*. 2nd ed... Lanham : Rowman & Littlefield, 2015.

Reference: Stuart, David E.. *Anasazi America: Seventeen Centuries on the Road from Center Place*. 2nd ed... Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press, 2014.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 2

Notes: The two tiers of religious hierarchical leadership may correspond to the inhabitants of Great Houses within Chaco Canyon and the inhabitants of outlier Great Houses throughout the Chaco World. Such an idea has been proposed (Lekson 2015; Stuart 2014).

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *The Chaco Meridian: One Thousand Years of Political and Religious Power in the Ancient Southwest*. 2nd ed... Lanham : Rowman & Littlefield, 2015.

Reference: Stuart, David E.. *Anasazi America: Seventeen Centuries on the Road from Center Place*. 2nd ed... Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press, 2014.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Oral traditions of Pueblo and Diné people explicitly state that Chacoan religious leader had supernatural powers (see quotations in Weiner 2023:14-15)

Reference: Weiner, Robert S. . "it Shows My Way": An Archaeology of Roads, Religion, and Power in the Chaco World. . Phd Dissertation. Department of Anthropology, University of Colorado Boulder: Boulder, 2023.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
 - Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: There was no written language in the Chaco culture.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

- ↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 40

Notes: This is a rough estimate based on the idea that an average Chacoan Great House community consists of a Great House (1,225 sq. m on average), multiple road segments (9 m wide by 100 m long, as a broad average), and approximately 25 community houses (200 sq m. on average).

- ↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 14176

Notes: Pueblo Bonito

- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 9

- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 1225

- ↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 6

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 80

Notes: This is a rough estimate. While small houses are present at Chaco Canyon, the vast majority of the built environment consists of religious monumental architecture (Great Houses, Great Kivas, and roads).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Pueblo Bonito contained multiple mortuary crypts, one of which held the remains of 14 individuals belonging to a single matrilineal dynasty (Kennett et al. 2017). While Pueblo Bonito likely held other associations, one was certainly to serve as a monumental tomb for an important lineage.

Reference: Kennett, Douglas J., Stephen Plog, Richard J. George, Brendan J. Culleton, Adam S. Watson, Pontus Skoglund, Nadin Rohland, et al.. "Archaeogenomic Evidence Reveals Prehistoric Matrilineal Dynasty" 8, no. 1 (February 21, 2017). <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14115>.

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: Chaco Canyon is notable for its lack of any clear cemetery, much less a monumental one.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The categorization of Chacoan Great Houses is contested. They have been interpreted as both temples (Weiner and Smith 2021) and palaces (Lekson 2015). Such categories are, of course, blurry in many ancient contexts.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *The Chaco Meridian: One Thousand Years of Political and Religious Power in the Ancient Southwest*. 2nd ed... Lanham : Rowman & Littlefield, 2015.

Reference: Weiner, Robert S., and Ema L. Smith. "Great Houses for Whom?: Chacoan Monumental Architecture in Cross-cultural, Cognitive, and Ethnohistorical Perspective" 14, no. 2 (April 3, 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1080/1751696x.2021.1918390>.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: A collection of painted wooden artifacts in Chetro Ketl have been interpreted as an altar (Vivian et al. 1978). Vivian, R. Gwinn, Dulce N. Dodgen, and Gayle H. Hartmann 1978 *Wooden Ritual Artifacts from Chaco Canyon, New Mexico*. Anthropological Papers of the University of

Arizona, Vol. 2. The University of Arizona Press, Tucson.

Reference: Vivian, R. Gwinn, Dulce N. Dodgen, and Gayle H. Hartmann. *Wooden Ritual Artifacts from Chaco Canyon, New Mexico*. Anthropological Papers of the University of Arizona, Vol. 2. Tucson: University of Arizona Press, 1978.

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Bonito Phase Chaco Great Houses have plazas that were likely used for gatherings. The open space between Pueblo Bonito and Chetro Ketl associated with the Amphitheatre may also have been a gathering area (Loose 2008). McElmo Phase Great Houses in Chaco Canyon are notable for their lack of plazas.

Reference: Loose, Richard W.. "Tse'biinaholts'a Yalti (curved Rock That Speaks)" 1, no. 1 (January 2008). <https://doi.org/10.2752/175169608783489080>.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Bi-wall structures

– Yes [specify]: Tri-wall structures

– Yes [specify]: Great Kivas

Notes: Great Kivas are circular, semi-subterranean masonry structures that most archaeologists agree were used for ritual gatherings in Chacoan society. See Van Dyke 2007a

Reference: Van Dyke, Ruth M. . "Great Kivas in Time, Space, and Society". In *The Architecture of Chaco Canyon, New Mexico*, 93-126. Salt Lake City: The University of Utah Press, 2007.

– Yes [specify]: Roads

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: The main evidence for religious iconography in Chacoan society comes from rock art (see Gilpin 2021) and human effigy vessels of tattooed bodies (Franklin and Reed 2016; Pepper 1906). Figurative iconography on Chacoan ceramics is rare, though painted Dogoszhi-style designs may have communicated religious ideas (Ortman and Traugott 2018; Plog 2003).

Reference: Franklin, Hayward H., and Lori S. Reed . "Human Effigy Vessels from Chaco Culture Outlying Communities". *Pottery Southwest* 32, no. 1 (2016): 2-19.

Reference: Ortman, Scott G., and Joseph Traugott. *Painted Reflections: Isomeric Design in Ancestral Pueblo Pottery*. Santa Fe: Museum of New Mexico Press, 2018.

Reference: Pepper, George H.. "Human Effigy Vases from Chaco Cañon, New Mexico". In *Boas Anniversary Volume: Anthropological Papers Written in Honor of Franz Boas, Professor of Anthropology*

in Columbia University, Presented to Him on the Twenty-fifth Anniversary of His Doctorate, Ninth of August, Nineteen Hundred and Six, 320-34. New York: G. E. Stechert & Co., 1906.

Reference: Plog, Stephen. "Exploring the Ubiquitous Through the Unusual: Color Symbolism in Pueblo Black-on-white Pottery" 68, no. 4 (October 2003). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3557067>.

Reference: Gilpin, Dennis . "Rock Art in the Chaco Landscape". In *The Greater Chaco Landscape: Ancestors, Scholarship, and Advocacy*, edited by Ruth M. Van Dyke and Carrie C. Heitman, 95-134. Louisville: University Press of Colorado, 2021.

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- On persons
- At home
- Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Chacoan rock art depicts zoomorphic beings that are not represented in nature.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Chacoan rock art depicts horned flute-playing anthropomorphs.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not known whether Chacoan geometric imagery represents divine beings.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Humans are depicted in Chacoan rock art and effigy vessel ceramics.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Spirals are the most common rock art motif at Chaco Canyon and throughout the Chaco World (Gilpin 2021; Kolber and Yoder 2008).

Reference: Gilpin, Dennis . "Rock Art in the Chaco Landscape". In *The Greater Chaco Landscape: Ancestors, Scholarship, and Advocacy*, edited by Ruth M. Van Dyke and Carrie C. Heitman, 95-134. Louisville: University Press of Colorado, 2021.

Reference: Kolber, Jane, and Donna Yoder. "The Spirals of Chaco Canyon". In *Chasing Chaco and the Southwest: Papers in Honor of Frances Joan Mathien*, edited by Thomas C. O'Laughlin, Regge N. Wiseman, and Cordelia T. Snow, *Papers of the Archaeological Society of New Mexico* 34:107-15. Albuquerque: Archaeological Society of New Mexico, 2008.

– Yes

Notes: The Tau shape was also an aspect of Chacoan religious iconography, which was used for public-facing doorways into Great Houses and incorporated into ceramics (Lekson 2105; Ortman and Traugott 2018).

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *The Chaco Meridian: One Thousand Years of Political and Religious Power in the Ancient Southwest*. 2nd ed... Lanham : Rowman & Littlefield, 2015.

Reference: Ortman, Scott G., and Joseph Traugott. *Painted Reflections: Isomeric Design in Ancestral Pueblo Pottery*. Santa Fe: Museum of New Mexico Press, 2018.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Chaco Canyon itself was a sacred center, and other locales throughout the Chaco World were also considered sacred such as Kutz Canyon, Hosta Butte, the Chuska Mountains, Mt. Taylor, and Black Lake (see Van Dyke 2007 and Weiner 2023 for further discussion).

Reference: Van Dyke, Ruth M.. *The Chaco Experience: Landscape and Ideology at the Center Place*. Santa Fe: School for Advanced Research Press, 2007.

Reference: Weiner, Robert S. . "it Shows My Way": An Archaeology of Roads, Religion, and Power in the Chaco World. . Phd Dissertation. Department of Anthropology, University of Colorado Boulder: Boulder, 2023.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The sacredness of Chaco Canyon was fundamentally tied to landscape features: Fajada Butte, Threatening Rock, the canyon walls and canyon's orientation in relation to astronomy, and prominent mountains on the horizons (see especially Van Dyke 2007 for further discussion).

Reference: Van Dyke, Ruth M.. *The Chaco Experience: Landscape and Ideology at the Center Place*. Santa Fe: School for Advanced Research Press, 2007.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Chaco Canyon has long been interpreted as a pilgrimage site based on multiple lines of evidence: the mismatch between the estimated population of the canyon and labor needed to construct Great Houses, zooarchaeological evidence for feasting, periodic large-scale breakage of ceramics, the prominence of astronomical commemoration (in architecture and rock art), and the large-quantity of imported goods at Chaco (Judge 1989; Kantner and Vaughn 2012; Van Dyke 2007). Others are critical of the pilgrimage model and would disagree that Chaco was a pilgrimage center (Lekson 2018; Plog and Watson 2012).

Reference: Judge, W. James . "The Development of a Complex Cultural Ecosystem in the Chaco Basin, New Mexico." In *Proceedings of the First Conference on Scientific Research in the National Parks, Volume II*, edited by Robert M. Linn, National Park Service Transactions and Proceedings Series Vol. 5. :901-6. Washington, D.C.: National Park Service, 1979.

Reference: Kantner, John, and Kevin J. Vaughn. "Pilgrimage as Costly Signal: Religiously Motivated Cooperation in Chaco and Nasca" 31, no. 1 (March 2012). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2011.10.003>.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *A Study of Southwestern Archaeology*. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, 2018.

Reference: Plog, Stephen, and Adam S. Watson. "The Chaco Pilgrimage Model: Evaluating the Evidence from Pueblo Alto" 77, no. 3 (July 2012). <https://doi.org/10.7183/0002-7316.77.3.449>.

Reference: Van Dyke, Ruth M.. *The Chaco Experience: Landscape and Ideology at the Center Place*. Santa Fe: School for Advanced Research Press, 2007.

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that

some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Personal effects:

– Field doesn't know

Valuable items:

– Yes

Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: High status Chacoan leaders were buried with large quantities of turquoise (sometimes worked into mosaics), as well as shell and jet (Plog and Heitman 2010; Pepper 1909).

Reference: Plog, Stephen, and Carrie Heitman. "Hierarchy and Social Inequality in the American Southwest, A.D. 800-1200" 107, no. 46 (October 14, 2010). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1014985107>.

Reference: Pepper, George H.. "The Exploration of a Burial-room in Pueblo Bonito, New Mexico". In Putnam Anniversary Volume: Anthropological Essays Presented to Frederic Ward Putnam in Honor of His Seventieth Birthday, April 16, 1909, by His Friends and Associates, 196-252. New York: G. E. Stechert & Co., 1909.

Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Many Chacoan burials are accompanied by objects that can include ceramic vessels and ornaments of turquoise, shell, jet, or other stones (Akins 1986).

Reference: Akins, Nancy. *A Biocultural Approach to Human Burials from Chaco Canyon, New Mexico*. Vol. Reports of the Chaco Center 9. Santa Fe, NM: National Park Service, 1986.

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Other objects from daily living such as ground stone and basketry are present with some Chacoan burials (Akins 1986).

Reference: Akins, Nancy. *A Biocultural Approach to Human Burials from Chaco Canyon, New Mexico*. Vol. Reports of the Chaco Center 9. Santa Fe, NM: National Park Service, 1986.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: While no cemeteries have been found in Chaco Canyon proper, a burial ground is known near the Kin Bineola Great House (Harrod 2013).

Reference: Harrod, Ryan P. . *Chronologies of Pain and Power: Violence, Inequality, and Social Control Among Ancestral Pueblo Populations (AD 850-1300)*. Phd Dissertation. Las Vegas: Department of Anthropology, University of Nevada, Las Vegas, 2013.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Room 33 in Pueblo Bonito housed the burials of fourteen individuals related through their matrilineal line (Kennett et al. 2017).

Reference: Kennett, Douglas J., Stephen Plog, Richard J. George, Brendan J. Culleton, Adam S. Watson, Pontus Skoglund, Nadin Rohland, et al.. "Archaeogenomic Evidence Reveals Prehistoric Matrilineal Dynasty" 8, no. 1 (February 21, 2017). <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14115>.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: In middens

Notes: See Akins 1986.

Reference: Akins, Nancy. *A Biocultural Approach to Human Burials from Chaco Canyon, New Mexico*. Vol. Reports of the Chaco Center 9. Santa Fe, NM: National Park Service, 1986.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Horned flute-player anthropomorphs and other seemingly supernatural beings are depicted in Chacoan rock art and on Chacoan ceramics (Gilpin 2021). Overall though, "Chacoan rock art rarely depicts recognizable deities" (Gilpin 2021:119). Pueblo and Diné oral traditions about Chaco refer to the presence of supernatural beings in the Chaco World (see, for example, deities described in Haile 1979; the presence of kachinas living at White House [Chaco] in Stirling 1942).

Reference: Gilpin, Dennis. "Rock Art in the Chaco Landscape". In *The Greater Chaco Landscape: Ancestors, Scholarship, and Advocacy*, edited by Ruth M. Van Dyke and Carrie C. Heitman, 95-134. Louisville: University Press of Colorado, 2021.

Reference: Haile, Berard. *Waterway: A Navajo Ceremonial Myth Told by Black Mustache Circle*. Flagstaff: Museum of Northern Arizona Press, 1979.

Reference: Stirling, Matthew W. . *Origin Myth of Acoma and Other Records*. Vol. Bureau of American Ethnology Bulletin Vol. 135. Washington, D.C.: Government Printing Office, 1942.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Chacoan rock art depicts multiple different beings that are not known from the visible

world (e.g., horned flute players, anthropomorphs with spiral hands, lizard-human hybrids).

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: At present, there is no clear evidence for sacrifice in Chacoan society.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: At present, there is no clear evidence for sacrifice in Chacoan society.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While it is unclear if membership in the Chacoan religion is based on the destruction of property, there is evidence for the intentional breakage of pottery (see Toll 2001) and the deposition of significant quantities of turquoise, shell, and other precious substances in sealed deposits (Heitman 2015; Mills 2010).

Reference: Toll, H. Wolcott. "Making and Breaking Pots in the Chaco World" 66, no. 1 (January 2001). <https://doi.org/10.2307/2694318>.

Reference: Heitman, Carrie C. , and Stephen Plog. "The House of Our Ancestors: New Research on the Prehistory of Chaco Canyon, New Mexico, A.D. 800-1200". In *Chaco Revisited: New Research on the Prehistory of Chaco Canyon, New Mexico*, edited by Carrie C. Heitman, 215-48. Tucson: University of Arizona Press, 2015.

Reference: Mills, Barbara J. . "Remembering While Forgetting: Depositional Practice and Social Memory at Chaco". In *Contemporary Archaeology in Theory: The New Pragmatism*, edited by Robert W. Preucel and Stephen A. Mrozowski, 362-84. Oxford: Willey-Blackwell, 2010.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It's not known if the Chacoan religion required participation in household rituals. Domestic ritual deposits, however, mirror those found in more monumental religious architecture (Heitman 2015).

Reference: Heitman, Carrie C. , and Stephen Plog. "The House of Our Ancestors: New Research on the Prehistory of Chaco Canyon, New Mexico, A.D. 800-1200". In *Chaco Revisited: New Research on the Prehistory of Chaco Canyon, New Mexico*, edited by Carrie C. Heitman, 215-48. Tucson: University of Arizona Press, 2015.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Those advocating for pilgrimage models of Chacoan religious dynamics would likely argue that participation in larger gatherings at Chaco Canyon, for at least some segment of the population, were a requirement of membership in the religious group.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: There is significant debate regarding Chaco Canyon's political organization, though most contemporary scholars would concede that if not a state proper (Lekson 2018; Wilcox 2004), Chaco was at least a state-like house society (Heitman 2015; Mills 2018) or chiefdom.

Reference: Heitman, Carrie C. , and Stephen Plog. "The House of Our Ancestors: New Research on the Prehistory of Chaco Canyon, New Mexico, A.D. 800-1200". In *Chaco Revisited: New Research on the Prehistory of Chaco Canyon, New Mexico*, edited by Carrie C. Heitman, 215-48. Tucson: University of Arizona Press, 2015.

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Reference: Mills, Barbara J. . "What's New in Chaco Research?". *Antiquity* 92, no. 364 (2018): 855-69.

Reference: Wilcox, David R. . "The Evolution of the Chaco Polity". In *Chimney Rock: The Ultimate Outlier*, edited by J. McKim Malville, 163-86. Lanham: Lexington Books, 2004.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some suggest that Chaco Canyon served as a redistribution hub for maize that helped provide a safety net for participants in the Chaco regional system / religion (Judge 1979; Lekson 2018; Stuart 2014), though such proposals are not widely accepted.

Reference: Judge, W. James . "The Development of a Complex Cultural Ecosystem in the Chaco Basin, New Mexico.". In Proceedings of the First Conference on Scientific Research in the National Parks, Volume II,, edited by Robert M. Linn, National Park Service Transactions and Proceedings Series Vol. 5. :901-6. Washington, D.C.: National Park Service, 1979.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. A Study of Southwestern Archaeology. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, 2018.

Reference: Stuart, David E.. Anasazi America: Seventeen Centuries on the Road from Center Place. 2nd ed... Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press, 2014.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some suggest that Chaco Canyon served as a redistribution hub for maize that helped provide a safety net for participants in the Chaco regional system / religion (Judge 1979; Judge et al 1981; Lekson 2018; Stuart 2014), though such proposals are not widely accepted.

Reference: Judge, W. James . "The Development of a Complex Cultural Ecosystem in the Chaco Basin, New Mexico.". In Proceedings of the First Conference on Scientific Research in the National Parks, Volume II,, edited by Robert M. Linn, National Park Service Transactions and Proceedings Series Vol. 5. :901-6. Washington, D.C.: National Park Service, 1979.

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Reference: Stuart, David E.. Anasazi America: Seventeen Centuries on the Road from Center Place. 2nd ed... Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press, 2014.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Lekson (2015, 2018) has argued that food storage was one purpose of Great Houses in Chaco Canyon based on the evidence of sealable doorways with secondary jambs in Pueblo Bonito. No large scale remnants of maize, however, have been recovered from Great House rooms, so more evidence is needed to assess the question of public food storage in Chacoan society.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *The Chaco Meridian: One Thousand Years of Political and Religious Power in the Ancient Southwest*. 2nd ed... Lanham : Rowman & Littlefield, 2015.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *A Study of Southwestern Archaeology*. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, 2018.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Some of the water management infrastructure present in Chaco Canyon was likely created through the organization of Chacoan religious leaders and by group members (Scarborough et al. 2018; Wills et al. 2023).

Reference: Scarborough, Vernon L., Samantha G. Fladd, Nicholas P. Dunning, Stephen Plog, Lewis A. Owen, Christopher Carr, Kenneth B. Tankersley, et al.. "Water Uncertainty, Ritual Predictability and Agricultural Canals at Chaco Canyon, New Mexico" 92, no. 364 (August 2018). <https://doi.org/10.15184/aqy.2018.114>.

Reference: Wills, W. H., Katharine Williams, Patricia L. Crown, and Wetherbee Dorshow. "The Bonito Paleochannel in Chaco Canyon, New Mexico: Recent Research and Implications for Causality and Effects" 90, no. 1 (October 4, 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00231940.2023.2258322>.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that Chacoan water management infrastructure was created/provided by some other social grouping than a large-scale Chaco religion.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: Chacoan roads were used for travel/transportation in some cases and likely mark the result of labor investment by adherents of Chacoan religion (Weiner 2023).

Reference: Weiner, Robert S. . "it Shows My Way": An Archaeology of Roads, Religion, and Power in the Chaco World. . Phd Dissertation. Department of Anthropology, University of Colorado Boulder: Boulder, 2023.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is possible that Chacoan roads were created/provided by some other social grouping than a large-scale Chaco religion.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Lekson (2015, 2018) has argued that leaders in Chaco Canyon levied tribute from throughout the Chaco World, as evidenced by the accumulation of imported pottery, high elevation timbers, turquoise, and non-local maize in Chaco Canyon's Great Houses with no clear corresponding exported good(s). Furthermore, contributing to Great House construction labor may have been a form of taxation / tribute. Mechanisms other than taxation may account for this pattern, however, and there is no consensus within the field.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *The Chaco Meridian: One Thousand Years of Political and Religious Power in the Ancient Southwest*. 2nd ed... Lanham : Rowman & Littlefield, 2015.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *A Study of Southwestern Archaeology*. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, 2018.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Wilcox (2004) and Lekson (2018) suggest Chacoan society had something akin to an institutionalized military / police force, though clear evidence is lacking.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *A Study of Southwestern Archaeology*. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, 2018.

Reference: Wilcox, David R. . "The Evolution of the Chaco Polity". In *Chimney Rock: The Ultimate Outlier*, edited by J. McKim Malville, 163–86. Lanham: Lexington Books, 2004.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Wilcox (2004) and Lekson (2018) suggest Chacoan society had something akin to an institutionalized military / police force, though clear evidence is lacking.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *A Study of Southwestern Archaeology*. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, 2018.

Reference: Wilcox, David R. . "The Evolution of the Chaco Polity". In *Chimney Rock: The Ultimate Outlier*, edited by J. McKim Malville, 163–86. Lanham: Lexington Books, 2004.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for institutionalized judges in Chacoan society.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for institutionalized judges in Chacoan society.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Harrod (2013) has provided bioarchaeological evidence for the use of violence as a technology of social control in Chacoan society, perpetuated by Chacoan elites.

Reference: Harrod, Ryan P. . Chronologies of Pain and Power: Violence, Inequality, and Social Control Among Ancestral Pueblo Populations (AD 850-1300). Phd Dissertation. Las Vegas: Department of Anthropology, University of Nevada, Las Vegas, 2013.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Harrod (2013) has provided bioarchaeological evidence for the use of violence as a technology of social control in Chacoan society. It is unclear whether such violence included execution or strictly corporal punishment.

Reference: Harrod, Ryan P. . Chronologies of Pain and Power: Violence, Inequality, and Social Control Among Ancestral Pueblo Populations (AD 850-1300). Phd Dissertation. Las Vegas: Department of Anthropology, University of Nevada, Las Vegas, 2013.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: Harrod (2013) has provided bioarchaeological evidence for the use of violence as a technology of social control in Chacoan society.

Reference: Harrod, Ryan P. . Chronologies of Pain and Power: Violence, Inequality, and Social Control Among Ancestral Pueblo Populations (AD 850-1300). Phd Dissertation. Las Vegas: Department of Anthropology, University of Nevada, Las Vegas, 2013.

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Harrod (2013) has provided bioarchaeological evidence for the use of violence as a technology of social control in Chacoan society. An argument could be made that such violence was inflicted by a contingent of Chacoan society separate from the religious group.

Reference: Harrod, Ryan P. . *Chronologies of Pain and Power: Violence, Inequality, and Social Control Among Ancestral Pueblo Populations (AD 850-1300)*. Phd Dissertation. Las Vegas: Department of Anthropology, University of Nevada, Las Vegas, 2013.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for formal legal codes in Chacoan society.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence for formal legal codes in Chacoan society.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Wilcox (2004) and Lekson (2018) suggest Chacoan society had something akin to an institutionalized military / police force, though clear evidence is lacking.

Reference: Wilcox, David R. . "The Evolution of the Chaco Polity". In *Chimney Rock: The Ultimate Outlier*, edited by J. McKim Malville, 163–86. Lanham: Lexington Books, 2004.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *A Study of Southwestern Archaeology*. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, 2018.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Wilcox (2004) and Lekson (2018) suggest Chacoan society had something akin to an institutionalized military / police force, though clear evidence is lacking. If such a force existed, it may have been separate from the religious institution.

Reference: Wilcox, David R. . "The Evolution of the Chaco Polity". In *Chimney Rock: The Ultimate Outlier*, edited by J. McKim Malville, 163–86. Lanham: Lexington Books, 2004.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *A Study of Southwestern Archaeology*. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, 2018.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Wilcox (2004) and Lekson (2018) suggest Chacoan society had something akin to an institutionalized military / police force, though clear evidence is lacking. If such a force existed, it may have been separate from the religious institution.

Reference: Wilcox, David R. . "The Evolution of the Chaco Polity". In *Chimney Rock: The Ultimate Outlier*, edited by J. McKim Malville, 163–86. Lanham: Lexington Books, 2004.

Reference: Lekson, Stephen H.. *A Study of Southwestern Archaeology*. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press, 2018.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are numerous proposals that religious leaders at Chaco Canyon maintained a ritual calendar for the entire Chaco polity (Judge and Malville 2004; Van Dyke 2007). Certainly, solstices, equinoxes, and lunar standstills were marked in Chacoan religious architecture and rock art (Sofaer 2007) and were important for the marking of time. The existence of a formal calendar, however, is not clearly evidenced through archaeology.

Reference: Van Dyke, Ruth M.. *The Chaco Experience: Landscape and Ideology at the Center Place*. Santa Fe: School for Advanced Research Press, 2007.

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Reference: Judge, W. James, and J. McKim Malville. "Calendrical Knowledge and Ritual Power". In *Chimney Rock: The Ultimate Outlier*, edited by J. McKim Malville, 151–62. Lanham: Lexington Books, 2004.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: While religious leaders in Chaco Canyon may have imported much of their food, participants in the Chaco religion as a whole were engaged in food procurement via maize-bean-squash agriculture, hunting, and gathering.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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<https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1014564624013>.

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